

Structural Studies on Dealuminated Scolecite

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The composition, structural characteristics and unit cell dimensions have been determined for dealuminized NH_4 -scolecite and Na-scolecite samples having Si/Al ratios of 1.73–3.15 and 1.84–3.60 respectively. The lattice contractions which occur on aluminium removal are strongly anisotropic and have been confirmed by ir spectra and X-ray diffraction studies. An explanation for differing dependence of the a , b and c lattice parameters on the Si/Al ratio has been proposed. Strong additional effects are observed in NaOH treated dealuminated samples due to smaller size of Na^+ ions in comparison to NH_4^+ ions.

The natural fibrous zeolite with an idealized chemical composition of $\text{Ca}_8(\text{AlO}_2)_{16}(\text{SiO}_2)_{24}\cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is abundantly available as cavity filling and vein deposit in the Deccan basalts around Pune and parts of Saurashtra in India. Its structure as solved by Heyl has monoclinic crystal system with cell parameters $a = 9.848 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 19.978 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.522 \text{ \AA}$ and $\beta = 110^\circ$ in its calcium form. Several studies have been reported about the ion exchange² and catalytic properties of scolecite³. Siliceous scolecite can be readily prepared by removal of framework aluminium by acid extraction without significant loss of crystallinity⁴. Generally higher silica content is associated with better thermal stability⁵.

The purpose of this research is to produce low cost dealuminated zeolite derivative of scolecite of improved thermal stability which can be used in various industrial processes. In the present work the variation in each of the three unit cell dimensions have been determined and infrared spectroscopic studies carried out for a series of acid dealuminated scolecite of Si/Al ratio of 1.56–3.60.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis of the NH_4OH and NaOH treated samples (Table 1) shows the removal of exchangeable calcium cations and its conversion into ammonium and sodium form. Elemental analysis also indicates the extent of dealumination by different acid treatments and changes in Si/Al molar ratios. It can be seen from the elemental data that prepared derivatives of scolecite contain high silica/alumina ratio as compared to original scolecite. High surface area of the post-heated derivatives (Table 2) is a direct evidence of the thermal stability of the prepared derivatives. Several reaction mechanisms have been suggested to explain framework stabilization upon dealumination^{6–8}. Earlier Kerr⁹ proposed that thermal stability of dealuminated highly siliceous zeolite derivatives are due to more Si–O–Si bond formation. NaOH treated samples are more dealuminated in comparison to NH_4OH treated samples which may be due to removal of framework aluminium in the soluble NaAlO_2 form by ion exchange¹⁰.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF NH_4OH TREATED AND NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE SAMPLES

Treatment	Composition	% Dealumination	Si/Al molar ratio
NH ₄ OH treated scolecite :			
Original	$\text{Ca}_{8.0}[\text{Al}_{16}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{80}]\cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Nil	1.56
0.5 N HCl	$(\text{NH}_4^+)_{13.82}[\text{Al}_{13.82}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{71.3}(\text{OH})_{8.704}]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	13.6	1.73
1 N HCl	$(\text{NH}_4^+)_{11.34}[\text{Al}_{11.34}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{61.38}(\text{OH})_{18.62}]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	29.1	2.12
2 N HCl	$(\text{NH}_4^+)_{11.36}[\text{Al}_{10.36}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{57.48}(\text{OH})_{22.52}]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	35.2	2.32
4 N HCl	$(\text{NH}_4^+)_{7.6}[\text{Al}_{17.6}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{46.4}(\text{OH})_{33.6}]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	52.5	3.15
NaOH treated scolecite :			
0.5 N HCl	$\text{Na}^+_{3.04}[\text{Al}_{13.04}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{68.16}(\text{OH})_{11.84}]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	18.5	1.84
1 N HCl	$\text{Na}^+_{10.46}[\text{Al}_{10.46}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{57.85}(\text{OH})_{22.14}]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	34.6	2.29
2 N HCl	$\text{Na}^+_{8.97}[\text{Al}_{18.97}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{51.904}(\text{OH})_{22.14}]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	34.6	2.29
4 N HCl	$\text{Na}^+_{6.65}[\text{Al}_{16.65}\text{Si}_{24}\text{O}_{42.62}(\text{OH})_{37.38}]\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	58.4	3.60

TABLE 2—SURFACE AREA OF THE NH_4OH TREATED AND NaOH TREATED DEALUMINATED SCOLECITE DERIVATIVES

Sl. no.	Treatment	Surface area (m^2/g) at 70° (2 h)	Surface area (m^2/g) after heating at 650° (2 h)
NH ₄ OH treated scolecite :			
1.	Original	365	50
2.	0.5 N HCl	362	310
3.	1 N HCl	364	300
4.	2 N HCl	370	340
5.	4 N HCl	341	290
NaOH treated scolecite :			
1.	0.5 N HCl	369	315
2.	1 N HCl	375	323
3.	2 N HCl	378	302
4.	4 N HCl	380	342

Infrared spectral studies :

The infrared absorption spectrum of scolecite consists of all the characteristic bands of scolecite along with coordinated water¹¹ (Table 3). The OH stretching region shows bands at 3775–3400 cm^{-1} . The bands at 3775–3740 cm^{-1} in all the dealuminated samples can be attributed to silanol bands (Si–OH modes)¹². The medium intensity bands at

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3660–3740 cm⁻¹ in all the dealuminated samples reflect the degree of dealumination¹³. It can be seen from the ir spectral data that bands are more prominent in case of NaOH treated samples due higher degree of dealumination. The sharpening of the bands in the spectra of dealuminated samples have been attributed to an increase in degree of order within the framework¹⁴.

TABLE 3—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF SCOLECITE SAMPLES*

Hydroxyl stretching frequencies :							
Sl. no.	Sample	Si/A1 molar ratio	ν_{HOH}	ν_{A1OH}	ν_{SiOH}		
1.	Original scolecite	1.56	3440m				
2.	NH ₄ OH treated samples	1.73	3445m	3660m	3740m		
		2.12	3450m	3680m	3745m		
		2.32	3455m	3685m	3747s		
		3.15	3448m	3690m	3750s		
3.	NaOH treated samples	1.84	3450m	3700m	3755s		
		2.29	3455m	3715m	3770s		
		2.67	3460m	3720m	3775s		
		3.60	3468m	3740m	3775s		
Framework vibrational frequencies :							
Sample	Si/A1	T-O asym. stretch	T-O asym. stretch	Double ring	T-O bending	12 Ring pore open	
1.	Original scolecite	1.56	1035m	700m	580m	440w	370sh
2.	NH ₄ OH treated samples	1.73	1045s	710m	582m	445w	380sh
		2.12	1048s	725m	585m	448w	387sh
		2.32	1055s	728m	590w	450w	387sh
		3.15	1058s	730m	595w	452w	388sh
3.	NaOH treated samples	1.84	1068s	745m	580m	445w	380sh
		2.29	1070s	746m	585m	450m	385sh
		2.67	1073s	751m	588m	448m	385sh
		3.60	1085s	755m	610m	452m	385sh

* s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, sh = shoulder.

Ir spectra in the region of skeletal vibration (1200–300 cm⁻¹) of the dealuminated scolecite derivatives indicate that by increasing degree of dealumination the absorption bands become sharper probably due to more isotropic character of the vibrations of the T atoms (T = Si, A1)¹⁵. In vibrational region of the spectra the bands show higher frequency shift in comparison to original scolecite. This shift is more in NaOH treated samples than in NH₄OH treated samples showing higher degree of dealumination in NaOH treated samples. In vibrational region of the spectra the most intense band is observed at 1085–1045 cm⁻¹. This band is sensitive to Si/A1 ratio. The higher frequency shift is due to increase in silica content in the treated samples¹⁶. This strong shift to higher frequency is accompanied by a corresponding decrease in unit cell size which can be confirmed by the decrease in lattice dimensions¹⁷ (Table 3).

X-Ray diffraction analysis :

The presence of aluminate tetrahedra in a zeolite framework is expected to cause an expansion in the lattice. Conversely removal of aluminium results in a contraction of unit cell¹⁸. Cations can have a significant influence on lattice dimensions. These influences can be observed in the present study as cations varied from Ca²⁺ $\left\langle \begin{matrix} \text{NH}_4^+ \\ \text{Na}^+ \end{matrix} \right\rangle$. For scolecite of different compositions, marked anisotropic shifts in *a* and *b* are observed. Such distorting interactions are expected to be more pronounced with the smallest cations Na⁺ and would be minimized with the larger ammonium ion.

Unit cell dimensions : X-Ray powder diffraction patterns yield only averages of the unit cell dimensions of a zeolite, averages which could well be influenced by crystallite inhomogeneity or by partial structural collapse. X-Ray diffraction data (Tables 5–13) show reduction in the number of peaks due to production of defect structure after dealumination.

TABLE 4—VARIATION IN UNIT CELL PARAMETERS WITH Si/A1 MOLAR RATIOS IN NH₄OH TREATED AND NaOH TREATED DEALUMINATED SCOLECITE SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Sample	Si/A1	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	β
1.	Original scolecite	1.56	9.84	19.97	6.52	110°
2.	NH ₄ OH treated samples	1.73	9.84	19.95	6.52	110°
		2.12	9.84	19.91	6.52	110°
		2.32	9.84	18.89	6.52	110°
		3.15	9.84	18.83	6.52	110°
3.	NaOH treated samples	1.84	9.803	19.24	6.52	110°
		2.29	9.776	19.18	6.52	109.9°
		2.67	9.69	18.72	6.52	109.5°
		3.60	9.643	18.66	6.52	119.4°

TABLE 5—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF NATURAL ZEOLITE SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.936 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	11.652	100.00	110
2	16.075	26.86	001
3	16.310	39.44	030
4	23.640	12.51	220
5	26.952	54.44	230
6	29.732	64.78	141
7	33.642	14.76	060
8	35.802	17.19	160
9	37.287	23.20	061
10	39.240	20.91	161
11	46.670	12.08	401
12	51.077	16.69	113
13	53.547	22.62	172
14	58.225	14.90	182

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TABLE 6—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 0.50 N HCl NH₄OH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.936 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	11.137	17.11	020
2	15.405	52.63	120
3	24.109	10.72	220
4	28.078	18.61	050
5	35.569	17.19	160
6	39.246	100.0	161
7	46.573	10.25	401
8	54.572	9.84	091
9	68.94	9.84	104

TABLE 7—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 1 N HCl NH₄OH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.936 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	5.573	32.20	010
2	11.993	26.43	110
3	22.427	34.36	040
4	23.296	40.52	031
5	24.120	79.29	220
6	34.210	100.0	102
7	36.184	71.36	301
8	50.792	39.20	103
9	54.826	66.96	213
10	55.075	42.24	500

TABLE 8—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 2 N HCl NH₄OH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.936 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	15.868	97.48	120
2	17.104	16.41	011
3	20.669	36.92	130
4	29.353	100.0	221
5	33.929	65.63	051
6	39.133	17.45	202
7	42.016	33.90	142
8	44.538	45.01	052
9	49.880	16.41	252
10	52.886	43.33	441
11	74.645	16.41	392

TABLE 9—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 4 N HCl NH₄OH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.936 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	11.802	20.31	020
2	26.795	86.41	201
3	32.986	100.0	012
4	47.730	69.05	270
5	56.269	20.31	451
6	66.230	43.82	2,10,0
7	75.965	20.37	283

TABLE 10—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 0.5 N HCl NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	9.643	13.08	110
2	17.616	20.65	210
3	20.330	24.33	140
4	21.346	59.30	201
5	24.106	13.90	141
6	25.511	87.73	231
7	29.375	100.0	032
8	42.939	22.08	172
9	58.661	25.94	482

TABLE 11—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 1 N HCl NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	17.676	39.88	210
2	20.738	31.46	131
3	21.362	60.67	201
4	27.909	95.50	060
5	30.565	100.0	132
6	34.792	60.67	420
7	35.961	44.94	152
8	37.889	56.74	322
9	39.779	66.29	081
10	44.472	48.87	091
11	58.650	34.26	373
12	59.415	37.01	244
13	67.3689	12.92	741

TABLE 12—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 2 N HCl NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	18.131	22.71	121
2	21.538	45.78	201
3	23.335	56.41	221
4	27.723	69.59	320
5	29.927	100.0	160
6	31.168	42.85	202
7	35.531	36.26	350
8	38.469	39.56	080
9	39.064	39.19	003
10	44.044	28.93	500
11	57.671	19.04	3,10,1
12	59.884	26.37	580

TABLE 13—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 4 N HCl NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$)

Peak no.	2 θ	<i>I</i> / <i>I</i> _{max} %	<i>hkl</i>
1	9.864	13.07	110
2	17.346	20.66	200
3	21.824	86.74	201
4	28.703	78.73	060
5	29.313	20.44	311
6	29.566	100.0	032
7	30.861	47.03	132
8	35.107	18.83	400
9	36.445	17.38	420
10	38.780	51.12	421
11	40.828	21.88	081
12	41.805	14.11	033
13	42.773	23.10	133
14	59.410	24.96	453

The crystal chemistry of scolecite has been investigated by Foster¹⁹, and Alberti *et al.*²⁰. The variation in unit cell parameters of scolecite with aluminium contents is shown in Table 4. The *a* and *c* lattice parameters are essentially unaffected in dealuminated NH₄ scolecite while slight contraction was observed in *b* parameter. Whereas in NaOH treated dealuminated scolecite, *c* parameter is unaffected and *a* and *b* are showing contraction in comparison to original scolecite. The average Al–O and Si–O distances in aluminosilicate structure are 1.75 and 1.62 Å respectively. In the NH₄OH treated samples less dealumination is observed. So the integrity of the dealuminated scolecite structure in *a* direction is maintained and most of the damage of aluminosilicate framework is expected in *b* direction. In case of NaOH treated samples more dealumination is possible due to the distortion of aluminate framework by the small Na and Al ions interactions²¹. In this way aluminium removal is observed in both *a* and *b* directions. A correlation between Si/Al molar ratio and lattice parameter has been established (Table 4). Variation in lattice parameter *b* with different Si/Al molar ratio can be seen from Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Changes in lattice parameter *b* vs Si/Al molar ratio in scolecite.

The dealuminated derivatives described here were submitted to calcination at 650° and their X-ray diffraction pattern have been recorded (Tables 14–22). X-Ray diffraction analysis makes it evident that aluminium deficient post-heated derivatives are more crystalline after calcination as compared to original scolecite. So the material obtained by dealumination has good stability and good crystallinity. This stability is due to aluminium deficiency²². The X-ray data of post-heated derivatives show a shift of diffraction peaks to higher 2θ value as compared to original scolecite and pre-heated derivatives which is consistent with more siliceous framework. During the heat treatment Si–O–Si bond formation is possible due to elimination of hydroxyl nests as dehydroxylation²³.

TABLE 14—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF ORIGINAL SCOLECITE AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h (λ = 1.5418 Å)

Peak no.	2θ	I _{max} %	hkl
1	11.832	100.00	110
2	17.235	16.86	020

TABLE 15—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 0.50 N HCl NH₄OH TREATED SCOLECITE (λ = 1.5418 Å) AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h

Peak no.	2θ	I _{max} %	hkl
1	11.829	18.11	020
2	15.405	42.63	120
3	26.201	11.72	220
4	28.078	18.61	050
5	36.569	100.0	161
6	54.572	9.84	091

TABLE 16—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 1 N HCl NH₄OH TREATED SCOLECITE (λ = 1.5418 Å) AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h

Peak no.	2θ	I _{max} %	hkl
1	11.993	26.43	110
2	24.380	50.12	031
3	34.228	100.0	102
4	36.184	65.03	103
5	55.120	42.24	500

TABLE 17—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 2 N HCl NH₄OH TREATED SCOLECITE (λ = 1.5418 Å) AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h

Peak no.	2θ	I _{max} %	hkl
1	15.870	94.20	120
2	22.70	16.41	011
3	29.353	100.0	051
4	35.952	60.23	202
5	44.538	45.01	052
6	75.650	16.20	392

TABLE 18—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 4 N HCl NH₄OH TREATED SCOLECITE (λ = 1.5418 Å) AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h

Peak no.	2θ	I _{max} %	hkl
1	11.952	19.28	020
2	26.795	85.21	201
3	32.986	100.0	270
4	66.268	40.20	2,10,0
5	78.205	20.11	284

TABLE 19—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 0.5 N HCl NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE (λ = 1.5418 Å) AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h

Peak no.	2θ	I _{max} %	hkl
1	17.628	19.56	210
2	21.346	55.26	201
3	24.119	18.90	141
4	25.520	80.62	231
5	58.721	25.94	482

TABLE 20—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 1 N HCl NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE (λ = 1.5418 Å) AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h

Peak no.	2θ	I _{max} %	hkl
1	17.70	39.82	210
2	20.738	30.42	131
3	23.361	59.09	060
4	30.625	100.0	132
5	37.911	56.74	322
6	44.472	40.82	081
7	60.489	15.22	721

TABLE 21—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 2 N HCl NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h

Peak no.	2θ	$I/I_{\max}\%$	hkl
1	18.23	20.81	121
2	24.365	56.41	221
3	29.930	100.0	160
4	32.681	39.20	202
5	40.712	39.19	003
6	60.112	27.20	580

 TABLE 22—X-RAY DIFFRACTION DATA OF 4 N HCl NaOH TREATED SCOLECITE ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) AFTER HEATING AT 650° FOR 2 h

Peak no.	2θ	$I/I_{\max}\%$	hkl
1	17.362	22.21	200
2	21.921	80.31	202
3	29.622	100.0	032
4	32.961	47.68	132
5	35.268	20.21	420
6	41.852	15.21	033
7	60.212	25.96	453

Dealumination of a zeolite improves its catalytic activities^{24,25}. Many workers reported different findings regarding the fate of the structural defects left by aluminium removal²¹⁻²⁸. In the present condition dealumination has been done in low temperature and by strong acid treatment. It can be assumed that local crystallization of the framework occurs²⁹. The silica necessary for the process presumably originates in the destroyed surface layers of the crystallites and diffuse into the interior³⁰.

Conclusions :

It can be concluded from this study that the crystallinity of natural scolecite is retained even after 30 to 60% dealumination as revealed by ir and XRD studies. The changes in lattice parameters were determined from X-ray diffraction data for dealuminized scolecite with Si/Al molar ratio from 1.56 to 3.60. A plot of b vs Si/Al ratio (Fig.1) was non-linear and suggested that more dealumination is observed in b direction of the crystal of scolecite.

Dealuminated NH_4OH and NaOH derivatives have exceptionally high thermal stability as shown by their BET surface areas and X-ray diffraction data after calcination. They maintain good crystallinity after heating upto 650° , whereas the original scolecite collapsed at this temperature. A comparatively higher dealumination, unit cell shrinkage and a higher frequency shift of ir bands has been observed in NaOH treated samples.

An attempt has been made to dealuminate scolecite and convert it into highly siliceous zeolite derivative of improved thermal stability. Scolecite has been earlier used as adsorbent in chromatography for the separation of some amines, triphenylmethane, dyes, amino acids, carbohydrates, dicarboxylic acids etc.³¹. It has also been used as catalyst for cumene cracking³. In the present work,

structural modification of original scolecite has been carried out by dealumination, ammoniation and ion-exchange. Keeping in view that such structurally modified low cost zeolite derivatives promise for their widespread catalytic and adsorption application for various industrial purposes.

Experimental

The scolecite sample used was a fine white powder. Aluminium was removed from various samples by refluxing in hydrochloric acid solution of concentration 0.5–4 N. In a typical dealumination experiment, scolecite samples (Si/Al = 1.56; 5 g) were refluxed in HCl (50 ml) solution for 2 h for each preparation. After noting the pH, the solutions were heated for a few minutes, then filtered and washed well to remove any excess acid or aluminium species. Any residual calcium was removed by exchanging half portion of each solution with aqueous ammonia and the remaining half portion with concentrated 2 N NaOH at reflux for 2 h and the final pH noted. After being filtered and washed the samples were boiled for 2 h in water (1 dm³) and dried at 70° .

To check the thermal stability of original scolecite and dealuminated derivatives, one part of each derivative and original scolecite were heated in muffle furnace at 650° for 2 h. Then the X-ray diffraction pattern and surface area by BET surface area method were recorded.

The metal contents (Al, Ca, Na, Si) of the samples were determined by AES/ICP technique. C, H and N contents were estimated by a Perkin-Elmer analyzer. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the compounds were recorded on a Philips X-ray machine attached to a microprocessor using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ and $\text{FeK}\alpha$ radiations of wavelength 1.54 and 1.936 \AA respectively. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

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